

Name: _____

Here is a pre-test, just to see how much knowledge you already have about computing science. Your answers to this test will not count for your final score. Nevertheless, let's see how far you get. Good luck!

PART 1: Concepts

Here is a list of concepts. Write a short explanation of each one. If you don't know what it means, just write an 'X'.

Concept	Explanation
algorithm	
variable	
Input / output	
loop / repetition	
condition	
method / function	

PART 2:

There are three playing cards laid out in a row on a table; each card is labeled with a number. You are given the following sequence of instructions:

1. Compare the number on the left-hand card with the number on the center card
2. If the number on the left-hand card is greater than the number on the center card
 - 2.1 exchange the two cards
3. Compare the number on the center card with the number on the right-hand card
4. If the number on the center card is greater than the number on the right-hand card
 - 4.1 exchange the two cards

(a) On the table are the following cards:

24	2	15
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Describe the state of the cards after you carry out the instructions:

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(b) What is the purpose of the sequence of instructions?

PART 3:

Here is a sequence of instructions:

1. Stand at the origin facing to the North.
2. Turn left
3. Carry out 10 times:
 - 3.1 Move 5 steps
4. Turn right
5. Carry out 10 times:
 - 5.1 Move 5 steps
6. Turn right
7. Carry out 10 times:
 - 7.1 Move 5 steps

(a) If you carry out these instructions, you will follow a path that is the form of some letter in English. What it is? (You can also draw the path.)

(b) Add more instructions at the end of the list so that the path obtained will be a square.

PART 4:

Two groups of kids are competing in a relay race. There are 10 kids in each group. Each one runs to the other side of the yard and back, and hands over the baton (i.e. stick) to the next kid. It takes 5 minutes for each kid in the first group to run back and forth, and 7 minutes for each kid in the second group to run back and forth. The first group consists of Mark followed by Mary followed by Dan, and then the other 7 kids in their group. The second group consists of Eli followed by Molly followed by Steve followed by the other 7 kids in their group. See the following diagram:

- (a) Whose turn is it to run after Mary's?
- (b) Molly's turn comes before whose turn?
- (c) How much time will pass until it is Dan's turn?
- (d) How much time will pass until all members of the first team finish?
- (e) How much time will pass until all members of the second team finish?
- (f) How much time will the whole race take? Explain why you think so.

- (g) What will happen if Mary loses the baton while she is running?